

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF MAIZE/SOYABEAN INTERCROP SYSTEMS BY PARTIAL BUDGET IN THE GUINEA SAVANNAH OF NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Seven soyabean/maize planting schedule intercrop were evaluated in a field experiment at Mokwa (Guinea savannah agro-ecology) in Nigeria, during the 2012 and 2013 cropping seasons with a view of determining the planting schedule that will result in the highest net benefit. Experimental design was randomize complete block (RCB) with three replicates. Soyabean variety TGX1448-2E was intercropped with maize variety ACR-DMR-SRY using the following planting schedules: (1) Maize planted at 14 Days Before Planting Soyabean(14DBPS), (2) Maize planted at 7 Days Before Planting Soyabean(7DBPS), (3) Maize and soyabean planted on the Same Date(PSD), (4) Soyabean planted 14 Days Before Planting Maize (14DBPM), (5) Soyabean planted at 7 Days Before Planting Maize (7DBPM), (6) Sole soyabean, (7) Sole maize. Results obtained indicated that when maize was the main crop, optimum net benefit was obtained when maize was planted at 14 Days Before Planting Soyabean (14DBPS), while when soyabean was the main crop, optimum net benefit was obtained when soyabean was planted at 7 Days Before Planting Maize (7DBPM).

KEYWORDS: Maize, Soyabean, Intercrop, Total extra cost, Extra benefits, Net benefits.

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INTRODUCTION

Intercropping has been traditionally favoured by peasant farmers as it reduces the likelihood of total crop failure (Balasubramanian and Sekayange, 1991). Yusuf *et al.* (2004) reported that intercropping sorghum seedlings with soyabean on soyabean planting day resulted in optimum yields of the component crops. Yusuf *et al.* (2009)

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also reported that planting of cassava at 28 Days Before Planting Soyabean resulted in the highest gross yields of the component crops. Adeniyani and Ayola (2007) reported that under intercropping system that consisted of soyabean as one of the components, biological weed control was very effective through the smothering effects that the soyabean had on the weeds. Soyabean consist of more than 36% protein, 20% Oil, 30% carbohydrate, excellent amount of dietary fiber, vitamins and minerals (IITA, 2009). Its production is however yet to gain ground in many parts of Nigeria. One of the challenges that hinder the cultivation of soyabean in the savannah is the lack of information about the appropriate planting schedule, required for intercropping soyabean with cereals crops like maize for optimum net benefits of the component crops: thus the need to carry out this research.

The objective of this experiment was to determine the maize/soyabean planting schedule intercrop system required for optimum net benefits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field experiment was conducted at the National Cereals Research Station at Mokwa (Guinea Savannah agro-ecology) of Nigeria, in 2012 and 2013. Soyabean variety TGX 1448-2E was planted on the 14th of July in all treatments and intercropped with maize variety ACR-DMR-SRY, using the following planting schedules:- (1) Maize planted at 14 Days Before Planting Soyabean (14DBPS) i.e. 30th of June in both years. (2) Maize planted at (7DBPS) i.e. 7th of July in both years. Soyabean and maize planted on the same day (PSD), i.e. 14th of July in both years. (4) Soyabean planted at 14 Days Before Planting Maize (14DBPM) i.e. 28th of July in both years. (5) Soyabean planted at (7DBPM) i.e. 21st of July in both years. (6) Sole soyabean (planted on the 14th of July in both years). (7) Sole maize (Planted on the 30th of June in both years). Experimental design was randomized complete block (RCB) with three replicates. The experiment was planted on ridges on a (14 x 31 m) land area. The gross plot (4 x4 m) consisted of four ridges spaced 1.0m apart, while the net plot (3 x 2 m) consisted of the two central ridges of each plot. Maize seeds were planted two per stand, on the crest of the ridge at a spacing of (1 x 1m) to give a plant population of 20,000 plants/ha. Soyabean seeds were drilled on the crest of the ridge in between maize stands at a spacing of 0.05 m within the ridge and 1.0m between the ridge to give a plant population of 200,000 plants/ha. Fertilizer N P K (15-15-15) was band applied at the rate of 30 kg/ha to both crops. The maize plants were side dressed with 20 kg/ha N at tasseling. Weed control was achieved by hoe weeding at 3 and 6 weeks after planting. Crop yields were subjected to statistical analysis using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and significant means separated by the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) (Box et. al. 2005). Partial budget was used to compute the net benefits of soyabean/maize intercrop systems.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The intercrop treatment Maize planted at 14DBPS produced the highest net benefit of N259, 170 in 2012 (Table 1). Sole soyabean treatment produced a net benefit of N255, 000, indicating that a net benefit of N4, 17 0 was gained as a result of intercropping maize with soyabean at 14Days Before Planting Soyabean (14DBPS). Net benefits obtained at the other intercropping treatments were less than that obtained at the sole soyabean treatment in this year. In 2013, the intercrop treatment soyabean planted at 7DBPM produced the highest net benefit of N487, 500 (Table 2). The sole soyabean treatment produced a net benefit of N384, 040, indicating that a net benefit of N103, 460 was gained, as a result of intercropping soyabean with maize at 7Days Before Planting Maize (7DBPM). Net benefits obtained at the other intercrop treatments were less than that obtained at the sole soyabean treatment. In conclusion, farmer's choice of the maize/soyabean planting schedule intercrop system to adopt will depend on whether his main or most desired crop in the intercrop is either soyabean or maize. If maize is the main or most desired crop in the intercrop, the maize should be planted at 14Days Before Planting Soyabean (14DBPS) for optimum net benefits. On the other hand if soyabean is the main crop or most desired crop in the intercrop, the soyabean should be planted at 7Days Before Planting Maize (7DBPM) for optimum net benefits.

Table 1: Economic analysis by partial budget

Treatments	Maize	Soyabean	Extra benefits	Net benefits
	Yields (kg/ha)			
	2012			
1. Maize Planted @ 14DBPS	908.3a	1091.7b	₦309, 170	₦ 259, 170
2. Maize planted @ 7DBPS	641.7ab	1041.7b	₦272, 510	₦ 222, 510
3. Maize & Soyabean PSD	510.0abc	1125.0b	₦276, 000	₦ 226, 000
4. Soyabean planted @ 14DBPM	78.3d	1333.3ab	₦274, 490	₦ 224, 490
5. Soyabean planted @ 7DBPM	191.70d	1350.1ab	₦289, 190	₦ 239,190
6 .Sole Soyabean	-	1525a	₦305, 000	₦ 255, 000
7. Sole Maize	641.7ab	-	₦64, 170	₦ 14, 170

N.B.

- Extra costs:-Soyabean seeds (50kg/ha) = ₦ 10, 000, planting of soyabean = ₦ 5, 000, harvesting, threshing, winnowing and bagging of soyabean = ₦ 35, 000.
- Total extra cost = ₦ 50, 000
- Extra benefits:- Crop yields X (maize / soyabean) field price
- Net benefits :- Extra Benefits – Total Extra Cost
- Maize field price; ₦ 100/kg
- Soyabean field price; ₦ 200/kg

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Table 2: Economic analysis by partial budget

Treatments	Maize	Soyabean	Extra benefits	Net benefits
	Yields (kg/ha)			
	2013			
1. Maize Planted @ 14DBPS	2812.5ab	644.4d	₦ 410, 130	₦ 360, 130
2. Maize planted @ 7DBPS	2104.18ba	361.1d	₦ 282, 638	₦ 232, 638
3. Maize & Soyabean PSD	1287.5a	1188.8c	₦ 366, 510	₦ 316, 510
4. Soyabean planted @ 14DBPM	0.0d	2,166.7ab	₦ 433, 340	₦ 383, 340
5. Soyabean planted @ 7DBPM	375.0d	2,500a	₦ 537, 500	₦ 487, 500
6 .Sole Soyabean	-	2,170.2ab	₦ 434, 040	₦ 384, 040
7. Sole Maize	3500.0a	-	₦ 350, 000	₦ 300, 000

N.B

- Extra costs: - Soyabean seeds (50kg/ha) = ₦ 10, 000, planting of soyabean = ₦ 5, 000, soyabean harvesting, threshing, winnowing and bagging = ₦ 35, 000.
- Total extra cost = ₦ 50, 000.
- Extra benefits:- Crop yields X (maize / soyabean) field price
- Net benefits :- Extra Benefits – Total Extra Cost
- Maize field price; ₦ 100/kg
- Soyabean field price; ₦ 200/kg

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